

1 H19, DIO, IPW and other imprinting associated transcription engaged during lineage commitment to the
2 trophoctoderm in human embryonic stem cells.

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophoctoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here H19, DIO, IPW and
9 other imprinting-associated transcription engaged during lineage commitment to the trophoctoderm in
10 human embryonic stem cells.

11 Citations

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